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1 **Current velocity estimation using a lateral line probe**

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8 **Abstract**

9 Freshwater ecosystems are inhabited by a vast spectrum of organisms, each with their
10 own complex biotic-abiotic relations. Considering the management and conservation of
11 these environments, it is necessary to understand the underlying hydrodynamic
12 interactions to which aquatic organisms are subject. Outside of bulk flow properties
13 such as the time-averaged velocity, it is currently difficult or impossible to obtain
14 detailed observations of the fluid-body interaction using current measurement
15 technology. It is in this context that the lateral line probe (LLP) has been developed.
16 The LLP mimics the performance of flow sensing modalities present in many aquatic
17 vertebrates. Research in the last decade has demonstrated that such devices are able to
18 reproduce signals relevant to fish behavior and estimate the hydrodynamic stimulus
19 response of the lateral line. However in most cases, the application of LLPs have been
20 limited to idealized conditions, subject to rigorous calibration. In this paper we present
21 an algorithm that allows the use of LLPs for current velocity estimation without sensor
22 calibration. The method makes use of the fluctuations in the near-body pressure field
23 induced by fluid-body interactions and introduces a semi-empirical resampling process
24 based on the conservation of energy. The algorithm is calibrated using a closed flume
25 and measurements taken using a laser Doppler anemometer. Validation of the approach
26 is carried out by comparing results obtained with an acoustic Doppler velocimeter

27 (ADV) in a vertical slot fishway. The mean error as compared to direct measurements
28 with the ADV was found to be 0.11 m/s with a correlation of 0.92.

29 **Keywords:** lateral line probe; current velocity; field measurements; pressure sensor

30 **1. Introduction**

31 Freshwater ecosystems are among the most threatened habitats worldwide and their
32 management requires a comprehensive understanding of their complex ecological
33 relations (Mitsch, 2012; Jiang et al., 2015). Due to this complexity, it is not always
34 feasible to use existing measuring devices to accurately record field measurements of
35 biological significance, and thus the influence of many physical variables remains
36 poorly understood (Goettel et al., 2015). In this work, we present a new measuring
37 device, the lateral line probe (LLP) which can be used to measure the flow field and
38 extract hydrodynamic parameters from “the fish’s perspective”.

39 There are multiple tools to measure the hydrodynamic parameters in field conditions
40 (e.g. Doppler velocimeters, propellers, rotors, electromagnetic current meters, etc.).
41 However, none of them can be considered as the ideal tool due to the influence of
42 obstacles, suspended particles, or gas bubbles (Dombroski and Crimaldi, 2007; Mori et
43 al., 2007). Additional considerations may be complex calibration processes (MacVicar
44 et al., 2007) and the inefficiency of measuring in low flows (Hammond et al., 1986).
45 Despite these challenges, useful algorithms have been developed to cope with them
46 (Finelli et al., 1999; Mori et al., 2007).

47 In order to measure biologically relevant parameters, it is necessary to use sampling
48 rates in the range of natural hydrodynamic receptors from 1-150 Hz (Venturelli et al.,
49 2012), which lie outside the majority of available field measuring devices. Furthermore,
50 to establish the fluctuating components of flow signatures and turbulence metrics which
51 may be related to fish preferences, higher frequency acquisition is required (Silva et al.,

52 2012; Alexandre et al., 2013; Bleckmann et al., 2014).

53 It is within this context that our research in the application of LLPs arises, with the goal
54 of creating devices capable of mimicking the stimulus response of lateral lines the flow
55 sensing organs present in aquatic vertebrates. As its organic analog, the LLP consists of
56 a discrete set of sensing units distributed over the body which are able to sense local
57 mechanical changes in water particle motion (Dijkgraaf, 1963). Recent research in LLPs
58 has demonstrated their capacity to reproduce some of the functions and behaviors of
59 biological lateral lines (e.g. hydrodynamic mapping, object and prey detection, flow
60 classification, rheotaxis, etc.) (Chen et al., 2006; Yang et al., 2007; Klein and
61 Bleckmann, 2011; Salumäe et al., 2012; Muhammad et al., 2015).

62 These capacities suggest the interesting potential of this technology for ecological
63 studies of aquatic vertebrates. Furthermore, due to their high sampling frequency (250
64 Hz for the LLP used in this work), LLPs provide the opportunity to record interactions
65 between the sensor body and the surrounding flow field, making it possible to study the
66 flow field from the point of view of the aquatic organism (Tuhtan et al., 2015).

67 One of the main disadvantages of LLP systems is that the sensors require calibration
68 before and after each use due to small changes in the transducer signals caused by the
69 drift between sensors. Drift is primarily caused by sensitivity due to temperature
70 changes (Venturelli et al., 2012). Although the observed pressure changes will usually
71 be small, they do have the potential to bias estimates of the measurements.

72 In this work, we propose a new two-stage signal processing pipeline which can be
73 applied to estimate the time-averaged current velocity without the need for sensor
74 calibration. The first step of the algorithm applies frequency domain analysis of
75 pressure fluctuations over a sampling interval of several seconds. In the second step, the
76 Bernoulli relation is applied to resample estimates at the original acquisition rate.

77 **2. Material and methods**

78 **2.1. Sensing platform**

79 Our LLP consists of an acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) plastic device in the shape
80 of an adult, farm-raised rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) with a body length of
81 0.45 m. The body cavity has 16 pressure sensors (SM5420C-030-A-P-S) and two 3-axis
82 accelerometers (ADXL325BCPZ) (Fig. 1).The pressure sensors have full sensitivity
83 over a 0–207 kPa range.

84 The signals from the pressure sensors after two-stage amplification (AD8421ARMZ
85 and AD8656ARMZ) reach a resolution of 0.46 Pa/LSB (least significant bit). The signal
86 is then digitized with a 16-bit analog to digital converter (AD7682BSPZ). All signals
87 are acquired at 2.5 kHz and are oversampled 10x times by means of a microcontroller
88 (AT32UC3C1512) and stored at a 250 Hz sample rate.

89

90 Fig.1. Location of the 16 pressure sensors and 2 accelerometers in the LLP.

91 **2.2. Theoretical background**

92 **2.2.1. Current velocity estimation**

93 The current velocity (U) is defined as the magnitude of the velocity vector:

94
$$U = \sqrt{u_x^2 + u_y^2 + u_z^2} \quad (1)$$

95 where u_x , u_y and u_z are the longitudinal, transverse and vertical components of the
96 velocity vector, respectively.

97 The main approach used for the estimation of U in LLPs uses the Pitot equation derived

98 from Bernoulli's principle (2) (Dubois et al., 1974). This method considers pressure
 99 differences between the stagnation point (P_1 , nose sensor) and a second point on the
 100 body which registers the free-stream static pressure (P_2 , lateral sensors). As the lateral
 101 sensors experience the static and dynamic pressure, a semi-empirical correction factor
 102 (β_U) is applied to the equation (Salumäe and Kruusmaa, 2013) (2).

$$103 \quad \frac{\rho \cdot U^2}{2} = (P_1 - P_2) = \Delta P_{1,2} \quad \rightarrow \quad U = \sqrt{\frac{2 \cdot \beta_U \cdot \Delta P_{1,2}}{\rho}} \quad (2)$$

104 $\beta_{U,I}$ depends on the pressure sensors used to calculate P_2 as well as on the body shape.
 105 Although this method provides a way to directly relate pressure readings to velocity
 106 estimates in order to calculate ΔP , the sensors are typically subject to a calibration
 107 process before each individual measurement (Venturelli et al., 2012). This severely
 108 hampers the range of applications outside of the laboratory, making the use of LLP
 109 systems practically impossible for field applications.

110 In order to avoid sensor calibration, we created a signal processing pipeline which uses
 111 the pressure fluctuations to estimate the flow velocity (Fig. 2).

112
 113 Fig.2. Signal processing and resampling process flowchart.
 114 First, the pressure signal is separated in two terms via Reynolds decomposition: a time
 115 average component (\bar{P}), which captures the atmospheric pressure, hydrostatic pressure,
 116 the pressure due to any far-field effects, and the near-field pressure as the fluctuations
 117 about the time-averaged mean (p'). Fundamentally, the fluctuations experienced by the
 118 LLP are caused by the dynamic superposition of normal (pressure) and shear stresses
 119 induced by the flow and fluid-body interactions.

120 The stimulus response of fluid-body interactions increases with the increase of velocity
121 and turbulence, producing higher pressure signal fluctuations, which in turn are
122 translated into an average increase of the amplitude of the signal. To separate the
123 turbulence and velocity effects, the fast-Fourier transform is applied to the time-domain
124 signal (p'). Afterwards a band-pass filter (BPF) is applied (Venturelli et al., 2012).
125 Finally, linear regression is used to obtain the relationship between the mean amplitudes
126 of the remaining frequency components and the observed mean velocities.

127 There are two sets of parameters which must be determined in order to use this
128 algorithm under different hydrodynamic scenarios: the total signal duration and the
129 filter cutoff frequencies. Both should be determined and optimized using velocity data
130 with different turbulence profiles and depend on the body shape and spatial distribution
131 of pressure sensors along the LLP.

132 2.2.2. Resampling

133 The obtained velocity estimate is for the time averaged (\bar{U}). However, in order to
134 estimate the dynamic properties of the flow, such as the turbulence intensity, it is
135 necessary to resample the velocity at the original sampling rate. To do so, we use a
136 signal processing workflow that takes advantage of the continuous variables used in
137 relation (2) of the LLP. The workflow is summarized in Fig. 2.

138 **2.4. Experimental arrangement**

139 To determine the necessary parameters and to validate the proposed algorithm, two
140 different experiments were carried out: closed flume experiments (to calculate β_U) and
141 vertical slot fishway (VSF) experiments. These experiments were carried out with
142 different turbulence intensities in order to estimate filter parameters and evaluate
143 general performance of the algorithm.

144 2.4.1. Closed flume experiments

145 A complete description of the flume setup can be found in Kruusmaa et al. (2011).
146 Three replicates were used. Pressure readings were registered in flow increments of 0.05
147 m/s over the full range of speeds in the flume (0-0.5 m/s). Each flow was sampled for
148 30 s and before each new measurement the motor was run for 30 s for flow velocity
149 stabilization. In all cases the signal durations were determined by preliminary tests. Test
150 signals with longer durations (120 s) were acquired and reduced progressively. In order
151 to determine the optimal sampling duration the same frequency distribution was
152 maintained. The measurements were then analyzed at 125 Hz. This frequency provides
153 a statistically stable value for 1 s time averages, maximizing the trade-off between data
154 storage and processing computational time. Additional replicates, measured at 250 Hz,
155 were also used to evaluate the velocity fit calibration.

156 2.4.2. Fishway experiments

157 Two flow scenarios (Q_1 , Q_2) were studied in a 1:1.6 scale model of the VSF in Koblenz,
158 Germany (Musall et al., 2015). $Q_1 = 0.130 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ with a mean pool depth (h_0) of 0.520 m
159 in the measured pool and water drop (ΔH) of 0.058 m in the upstream slot and $Q_2 =$
160 $0.170 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ ($h_0 = 0.560 \text{ m}$ and $\Delta H = 0.078 \text{ m}$). In both scenarios, 3 horizontal profiles were
161 measured: $0.25h_0$, $0.40h_0$, and $0.60h_0$. Each point (Fig. 4(a)) was measured for 30 s.

162 The velocity profiles used in the algorithm calibration parameters ($0.25h_0$ and $0.40h_0$)
163 were recorded with a laser Doppler anemometer (LDA) (2D FlowExplorer System,
164 Dantec Dynamics) with an acquisition frequency of 1 Hz over a sampling duration of 60
165 s. Likewise, the profiles at $0.60h_0$ were used to evaluate the performance of the
166 proposed method. In order to achieve a higher sampling rate, profiles at this depth were
167 measured with an ADV (Vectrino, Nortek) at 25 Hz for 60 s. In both cases 60 s
168 provided a stable mean value for the measured velocities and turbulence parameters.

169 **3. Results and discussion**

170 **3.1. Mean velocity estimation**

171 The pressure distribution around the body of the LLP shows different patterns specific
172 to the body geometry (Fig. 3, a and b). The nose sensor logs the stagnation pressure, P_1 .
173 Across the lateral sensors, e.g. P_2 , the velocity will be closer to the current velocity flow
174 and consequently the pressure readings will be smaller (Fig. 3(a)). Ideally the graph will
175 be completely symmetrical; however even after calibration deviations persist primarily
176 due to non-uniform heat exchange which can result in an asymmetric distribution. This
177 reinforces the necessity of an alternative method for velocity measures.

178

179 Fig.3. Results of experiments: a) and b) Closed flume experiments, relative pressure distribution
180 over the LLP and pressure difference for different sensor combinations and body shapes. c) and
181 d) relation used in the algorithm and evolution of the error as a function of increasing signal
182 sampling duration.

183 The relation between current velocity and pressure difference were found to follow (2)
184 (Fig. 3(b)). The relation remains semi-empirical considering the assumptions made in
185 the Bernoulli approximation and non-ideal nature of the flow. Considering a given LLP
186 design, the velocity-pressure relation depends not only on the choice of the sensor
187 combination across which the pressure difference is calculated, but also on the body

188 shape and position of the sensors. Likewise, Salumäe and Kruusmaa (2013) observed
189 that when considering the best choice among lateral sensors along both sides, it was
190 found that P_2 was able to correct for small disorientations from the main flow current.

191 To calculate the cutoff frequencies for the BPF as well as the signal duration, data from
192 the closed flume and LDA was used. On average it was found that longer duration
193 signals provide better performance and fits (Fig. 3(c)). This was tested by first
194 determining optimal filter parameters (20 and 60 Hz) for the longest measurement
195 duration. Next, the duration was reduced to determine the trend of the error (Fig. 3(d)).

196 The shape of the confidence interval in the fit is explained by considering that the mean
197 amplitude of the frequency domain signal, \bar{A} must be 0 when the current velocity, \bar{U} is
198 0 m/s. The resulting fit using a linear regression equation therefore does not have a term
199 for the y-intercept (Fig. 3(c)). Due to this, the limit of low velocity detection can be
200 defined exactly as the noise ratio of the sensors used.

201 The LLP velocity estimate error decreases with increasing signal duration (Fig. 3(d)).
202 For durations higher than 15 s, the error remains reasonably constant. Likewise, from
203 the comparison of data between the closed flume and fishway it becomes apparent that
204 longer signal durations are advisable for regions with high levels of ambient turbulence.

205 **3.2. Fishway experiments and evaluation**

206 In order to demonstrate the performance under turbulent flow conditions without the
207 application of sensor calibration, the mean velocity profiles of a laboratory VSF were
208 studied with the LLP oriented against the global flow direction (parallel to the top and
209 bottom walls). Despite the flow complexity of VSFs, their velocity and recirculation
210 patterns are well-known (Rajaratnam et al., 1986). The typical pattern of these
211 structures is visible in the profiles estimated by the LLP and ADV (e.g. Fig. 4(a)).

212 The maximum velocity should fit approximately $\sqrt{2 \cdot g \cdot \Delta H}$, where ΔH is the water drop

213 in the slot and g stands for the gravity (Rajaratnam et al., 1986). ΔH decreases together
 214 with the discharge which is in line with the observed decrease in higher estimated
 215 velocities. The mean difference between ADV and the LLP is 0.111 m/s with a
 216 correlation of 0.92 (Fig 4(b)). From this result and Fig 3(c) and 4(b) it is observed that
 217 there is a systematic underestimation at lower velocities. This can be seen from the
 218 profiles of Fig 4(a) where the local higher velocities observed in the recirculation zones
 219 of ADV profile are likely produced by the overestimation of u_z and recirculation effects,
 220 probably due to sensor orientation. Considering all velocity components independently
 221 and the integration of bottom sensors could improve \bar{U} estimate. This will be
 222 investigated in future analyses of the VSF results for estimating turbulence metrics.

223
 224 Fig. 4. Evaluation. a) Comparison between the profiles estimated by the ADV and LLP in 0.17
 225 m^3/s and $0.6h_0$ scenario. b) Scatter plot of the measured velocities in the fishway with ADV and
 226 LDA vs LLP.

227 3.3. Resampling

228 The resampling method used in this work allows us to recover the velocity signal at the
 229 same sampling rate as measured by the LLP. Its performance has been evaluated at
 230 three locations with different turbulence properties (A, B and C, Fig. 4(a)). At each
 231 location, the turbulence intensity (I) was used for comparison, defined as the root-mean-
 232 square of u' divided by \bar{U} . Both devices deliver similar results: LLP: A=0.124,

233 B=0.419 and C=0.269; ADV: A=0.062, B=0.376 and C=0.371. Due to large differences
234 in the sampling rate (125 Hz vs 25 Hz) and sampling volume (the LLP uses the distance
235 between sensors) further research with high sampling frequency, e.g. particle image
236 velocimetry (PIV) under a range of turbulent flow conditions will be carried out.

237 **4. Conclusions**

238 This article presents a signal processing workflow for calculating the time-averaged
239 current velocity, U independently from sensor calibrations using a fish-shaped LLP. We
240 make use of the stimulus response of a fish-shaped pressure sensing array over several
241 seconds, where the recommended value of the LLP in this work was found to be ≥ 15 s.
242 In a second step, the signal can then be resampled at full temporal resolution.

243 The algorithms were compared to conventional velocity probes providing preliminary
244 results for estimating the current velocity in a complex 3D flow field. However, further
245 research is necessary to improve the methodology in order to make the probe a viable
246 alternative to conventional devices. Future work will focus on velocity component
247 estimation, comparing LLP estimates with PIV velocity measurements at high
248 frequency (>100 Hz) to study local hydrodynamics, especially the influence of body
249 orientation on LLP measurement accuracy.

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